

DEVELOPMENT OF CUSHIONING-BASED METHODOLOGY TO DESIGN SUSTAINABLE PAPER- BASED PACKAGING FOR HOUSEHOLD APPLIANCES

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Abstract: *Consumer goods are usually enclosed in protective packaging to protect them from vibration and impact shocks during handling and transportation. Bio-degradable materials such as molded pulp and honeycomb paper panels have emerged as formidable and sustainable alternatives to EPS. These materials exhibit distinct nonlinear and orthotropic behavior and can be characterized by a relatively high stiffness. These makes them far from being regarded as an ideal cushioning material. Due to the inferior paper-based packaging performance, the improvement of protective and cushioning properties relay on the structural optimization of the packaging design. With proper design in terms of minimizing the vibration transfer path to the product itself and by avoiding extensive plastic deformation it is possible to significantly enhance cushioning performance of paper-based packaging even at multiple impacts. This groundbreaking new approach has the potential to extend paper-based packaging design to more demanding packaging applications such as heavy and complex home appliances and with this drastically reduce the consumption of EPS. The article presents a method for the experimental determination of the honeycomb-material cushioning performance together with a paper-based packaging design methodology. The proposed concept is used to design the paper-based packaging for tumble dryer produced by Gorenje.*

Keywords: paper, cushioning properties, structural analysis, packaging

1 INTRODUCTION

Commercial goods are commonly encased in packaging buffers to protect them from damage due to vibration and impact shock during handling and transportation (Kun et al., 2017). The materials used to fabricate protective packaging are usually plastic foam such as EPS with good cushioning performance and cost-effective but not friendly to the environment (Andena et al., 2018). The growing trend towards the use of environmentally friendly packaging has led to an increase in the research and use of alternative biobased packaging solutions. Considering this paper-based packaging (molded pulp, honeycomb paper, etc.) already offers established sustainable packaging solutions that is recyclable, biodegradable and compliant with ISO 14000 and European Green Dot standards (Lye et al., 2004). Usually, the paper packaging solution are implemented for protection of lightweight structures such as small domestic appliances, electronic components, food products, etc.

Figure 1: Sustainable design of protective packaging using experimental-numerical approach

Although the paper-packaging materials and corresponding numerical design methods are already well established, they cannot be readily used to design packaging of heavy and complex home appliances for several reasons (Kun et al., 2017). Firstly, these materials exhibit high stiffness before plastic deformation which makes them far from being regarded as an ideal cushioning material. Moreover, the established paper packaging solutions have comparable cushioning performance to EPS only at low static loads and low drop heights (Kun et al., 2017). Therefore, to improve the cushioning performance, the design of the paper packaging rely on the numerical structural optimization to reduce vibration transmissibility and to increase

shock absorption in the case of single and multiple impacts (Kun et al., 2017; Fadiji et al., 2018).

In this paper, a combined experimental and numerical approach is proposed to design a honeycomb paper-based packaging (Fig. 1) that has the potential to extend its applicability to more demanding packaging applications such as heavy home appliances. The research first presents the phenomenological experimental investigation to characterize the dynamics and cushioning properties of honeycomb paper packaging materials. Based on experimentally determined cushioning and material properties, the finite element method (FEM) was proposed to optimize the packaging design and thus improve its protective and cushioning performance.

2 EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION OF HONEYCOMB-PAPER CUSHIONING PROPERTIES

Cushioning of packaging materials is typically evaluated in terms of the maximum deceleration versus the static stress for a specific drop height and cushion thickness. This enables one to obtain cushioning curve that defines minimum cushioning area to obtain best shock absorption. These standard methods provide a general guidance to the evaluation of cushioning performance. Here the standard impact-based test facility is proposed as shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 2: Experimental determination of honeycomb cushioning characteristics;
a) Experimental test rig, b) Specimen before and after testing

In Fig. 3 the cushioning curves obtained by measuring honeycomb panels with 20 mm thickness are presented. The curves were obtained by performing the measurement with test samples of different cross-sections and considering multiple successive impacts. It can be observed that the cushioning curves

change significantly in the event of consecutive impacts. The reason for this is that the honeycomb structure is deformed and as a result loses its cushioning ability, especially at high static contact pressures.

Figure 3: Measured cushioning curves for honeycomb panel of height 20mm at multiple subsequent impacts.

The optimal static pressure for analyzed honeycomb panels (thickness 20 mm) is between 10 kPa and 15 kPa.

3 PAPER-BASED PACKAGING DESIGN METHODOLOGY

The paper-based packaging design methodology is demonstrated on the packaging design of the tumble dryer as shown in Fig. 4a. The entire packaging concept is based on folding through V-groove cuts without gluing. The principle of packaging folding can be clearly demonstrated by the unfolded and folded configuration of packaging corner (Fig. 4b).

Figure 4: Design concept of the paper honeycomb packaging for Gorenje tumble dryer; a) The packaging together with appliance, b) Folding concept

To enhance the packaging protective performance, a static analysis was firstly carried out to deduce the contact pressures due to the weight of the appliance (Fig. 5a). The calculated stresses on the bottom part of packaging are presented in Fig. 5b. The contact areas are deduced in such a way that they are close to the optimal pressure of 15 kPa to achieve the best cushioning performance. The static pressure analysis is carried out for both for the vertical impact and the impact from the side of the appliance.

Figure 5: Calculation of static loads on the packaging; a) Application of gravitational load, b) Calculated static pressures on the bottom part of the packaging

With an optimized packaging design, the simulation of loads caused by impacts during transport is then carried out. These loads are usually determined based on the acceleration measurements during standard transportations tests. This includes the drop test and the side impact test, also known as the slope test. In Fig. 6 the loads applied to the sidewall during the slope test are presented along with induced stresses on the appliance. These simulations make it

possible to identify stresses that could potentially lead to plastic deformation and breakage of an appliance.

Figure 6: The simulation of impact on the sidewall during slope test; a) Application of acceleration loads, b) Stresses on the appliance during impact

Based on the numerical simulations, the final concept of the packaging design is deduced and the prototypes of the packaging are produced as shown in Fig. 7. With the prototype packaging, it is then possible to conduct an actual transportation test and in that way finally validate the proposed concept of packaging design.

Figure 7: The actual prototype of paper honeycomb packaging; a) Packaged appliance in cardboard box, b) Inner view of packaging design

4 CONCLUSIONS

The proposed approach for paper packaging design is based on an interdisciplinary research that integrates the state-of-the-art dynamics simulation methods with the latest advances in paper material technology. It is demonstrated that suitable geometric design of honeycomb packaging

makes it possible to improve the paper packaging cushioning characteristics even at multiple transportation shock loads. The presented design methodology enables development of a sustainable and recyclable packaging solutions even for heavy home appliances. This will allow GORENJE to expand its sales on markets that have already taken significant regulations towards sustainability and recyclability.

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